

Synthesis and biological study of oxopyrimidines and thiopyrimidines of 2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-3-carbaldehyde

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Abstract : 2-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-3-carbaldehyde (1) was prepared from 2-aminopyridine through multi-step reaction. Compound 1 reacts with different aryl ketones in the presence of catalytic amount of 40% KOH to give (2*E*)-3-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-3-yl]-1-arylprop-2-en-1-ones (2*a-j*), which on cyclization with urea and thiourea in the presence of basic catalyst like KOH afforded 6-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-3-yl]-4-aryl-pyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones (3*a-j*) and 6-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-3-yl]-4-aryl-pyrimidin-2(1*H*)-thiones (4*a-j*). The antimicrobial evaluations have been performed for their antibacterial activity and antifungal activities.

Keywords : Imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine, oxopyrimidines, thiopyrimidines, antibacterial activity, antifungal activity.

Introduction

In the last decade much interest has been focused on the study of oxopyrimidine and thiopyrimidine derivatives. Several publications have pointed out the value of chlacones as biological agents and important intermediate for the synthesis of biologically important heterocycles. Some of the work reported from our laboratory¹⁻⁵.

Oxopyrimidines and thiopyrimidines are potential bioactive agents due to their wide spectrum of pharmacological activities like anti-inflammatory⁶, antimicrobial⁷, calcium channel blockers⁸, antihypertensive⁹, analgesic¹⁰, antitumor¹¹, antiviral¹², antibacterial¹³, anti-HIV¹⁴ and anticancer¹⁵. Looking to the diversified activities exhibited and in continuation of our work on the synthesis of biologically active heterocycles, we report here in the reaction of different aryl ketones with 2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-3-carbaldehyde in the presence of 40% KOH afforded (2*E*)-3-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-3-yl]-1-aryl-prop-2-en-1-ones (2*a-j*). Compounds (2*a-j*) on cyclization with urea and thiourea in the presence of basic catalyst like KOH afforded 6-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-3-yl]-4-aryl-pyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones (3*a-j*) and 6-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-3-yl]-4-aryl-pyrimidin-2(1*H*)-thiones (4*a-j*).

The structures of the synthesized compounds 3*a-j* and 4*a-j* have been confirmed by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data. All the synthesized compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity against various microbes under identical condition, the standard antibiotics were used for comparison purpose like amoxicillin, benzyl penicillin, ciprofloxacin and erythromycin against bacterial strains and greseofulvin against *Aspergillus niger*. All the newly synthesized compounds have been screened for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activity.

Results and discussion

Antimicrobial and antifungal activity :

The purified products were screened for their antimicrobial activity using the cup-plate agar diffusion method¹⁶ by measuring the zone of inhibition in mm. All the compounds were screened for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activity against different bacterial strains such as *Bacillus megaterium* ATCC 14518, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923, *Pasteurella aerogenes* ATCC 27883, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 25619 and fungi *Aspergillus niger* ATCC 9029 at 40 µg/mL concentration. Standard drugs like amoxicillin, benzyl penicillin, ciprofloxacin, erythromycin and greseofulvin were used for the comparison purpose (Table 1).

Table 1. Antimicrobial screening results of compounds 3a-j and 4a-j

Compd.	R	Zone of inhibition (mm)				
		Antibacterial activity				Antifungal activity
		<i>B. megaterium</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aerogenes</i>	<i>P. aeruginos</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
3a	C ₆ H ₅ -	12	17	14	15	15
3b	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	14	10	17	10	21
3c	2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	20	19	12	18	19
3d	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	11	14	11	12	17
3e	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	10	21	13	14	14
3f	2,4-(Cl) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	17	10	16	13	21
3g	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	14	13	14	17	16
3h	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	17	16	9	13	19
3i	4-SCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	13	14	14	18	13
3j	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	10	12	10	17	10
3k	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	18	11	22	12	17
3l	3-OC ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ -	19	13	17	21	14
4a	C ₆ H ₅ -	12	14	19	17	17
4b	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	10	16	11	14	21
4c	2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	11	19	13	13	16
4d	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	14	13	12	11	19
4e	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	17	12	10	12	13
4f	2,4-(Cl) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	18	11	14	14	12
4g	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	8	18	13	14	19
4h	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	11	16	17	10	15
4i	4-SCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	14	17	16	11	10
4j	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	17	14	14	12	16
4k	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	15	12	11	18	14
4l	3-OC ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ -	18	23	8	19	22
Amoxicillin		25	25	20	22	-
Benzyl penicillin		18	19	21	21	-
Ciprofloxacin		20	15	22	16	-
Erythromycin		22	21	19	23	-
Greseofulvin		-	-	-	-	26

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Thin layer chromatography using silica gel G (E. Merck) plates was used to access the reactions and purity of the synthesized compounds. All the products have been characterized by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral study. IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR-8400 spectrophotometer in KBr disc and noteworthy absorption levels (cm⁻¹) are listed. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker spectrometer (300 MHz) using TMS as an internal stan-

dard. Mass spectra were determined using direct inlet probe on a GCMS-QP2010 mass spectrometer. Elemental analysis were performed on a Carlo Erba EA 1108 elemental analyzer.

General procedure for preparation of (2E)-3-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3-yl]-1-aryl-prop-2-en-1-ones (2a-j) :

To a solution of 2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine-3-carbaldehyde (2.91 g, 0.01 mole) in methanol (25 ml) different aryl acetophenones (0.01 mole) were added. The content was stirred at room temperature for

Scheme 1

24 h in presence of catalytical amount of 40% KOH (0.5 ml). The resulting solution was poured onto crushed ice and the solid separated was filtered and crystallized from suitable solvent to give analytical pure products.

General procedure for preparation of 6-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3-yl]-4-arylpyrimidin-2(1H)-ones (3a-j) :

A mixture of (2*E*)-3-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3-yl]-1-aryl-prop-2-en-1-ones (0.01 mole)

and urea (0.60 g, 0.01 mole) in ethanol (25 ml) were refluxed in the presence of alcoholic KOH (1 ml) for 12 h. The excess solvent was distilled off and the residue was neutralized with dilute HCl. The separated solid was filtered out and crystallized from suitable solvent to give pure products.

3a : 6-[2-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3-yl]-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1*H*)-one : Yield 63%, m.p. 197 °C (Found : C, 63.64; H, 3.15; N, 12.85. Calcd. for

$C_{23}H_{14}Cl_2N_4O$ (433.29) : C, 63.76; H, 3.26; N, 12.93%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3359 (N-H str.), 3017 (C=C-H str.), 1665 (C=O str.), 1597 (C=N str.), 1448 (C=C str.), 1139 (C-N str.), 731 (C-Cl str.); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$), δ , ppm : 6.2 (1H, s, pyrimidine-Ha), 7.02 (1H, dd, J 7.1, 1.9, Ar-Hf), 7.25 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.31 (4H, m, imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-H), 7.45 (1H, d, J 1.8, Ar-Hd), 7.86 (1H, d, J 7.0, Ar-He), 9.1 (1H, s(b), pyrimidine-N-H); EI/MS m/z : 434, 355 (base peak), 394, 353, 318, 293, 264, 215, 177, 158, 140, 78.

3e : 6-[2-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-3-yl]-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)pyrimidine-2(1*H*)-one : Yield 72%, m.p. 167 °C (Found : C, 62.13; H, 3.54; N, 12.00. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{16}Cl_2N_4O_2$ (463.31) : C, 62.22; H, 3.48; N, 12.09%); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3252 (N-H str.), 3048 (C=C-H str.), 2978 (CH-CH str.), 1682 (C=O str.), 1566 (C=N str.), 1442 (C=C str.), 1367 (C-C str.), 1138 (C-N str.), 779 (C-Cl str.); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$), δ , ppm : 3.87 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 5.2 (1H, s, pyrimidine-Ha), 7.13 (1H, dd, J 6.9, 2.7, Ar-Hf), 7.15 (2H, dd, J 8.3, 1.6, Ar-H), 7.53 (4H, m, imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-H), 7.66 (2H, dd, J 8.3, 1.5, Ar-H), 7.73 (1H, d, J 2.6, Ar-Hd), 7.96 (1H, d, J 7.0, Ar-He), 10.3 (1H, s(b), pyrimidine-N-H); EI/MS m/z : 463.

3g : 6-[2-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-3-yl]-4-(4-chlorophenyl)pyrimidin-2(1*H*)-one : Yield 67%, m.p. 260 °C (Found : C, 58.99; H, 2.85; N, 11.94. $C_{23}H_{13}Cl_3N_4O$ (467.73) required : C, 59.06; H, 2.80; N, 11.98%); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3358 (N-H str.), 3075 (C=C-H str.), 1464 (C=C str.), 1658 (C=O str.), 1591 (C=N str.), 1146 (C-N str.), 785 (C-Cl str.); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$), δ , ppm : 6.22 (1H, s, pyrimidine-Ha), 7.14 (1H, dd, J 7.8, 2.89, Ar-Hf), 7.29 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.52 (4H, m, imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-H), 7.65 (1H, d, J 2.9, Ar-Hd), 7.80 (1H, d, J 7.7, Ar-He), 10.2 (1H, s(b), pyrimidine-N-H); EI/MS m/z : 468, 432 (base peak), 395, 356, 317, 294, 266, 217, 176, 159, 138, 78.

*General procedure for preparation of 6-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-3-yl]-4-aryl-pyrimidine-2(1*H*)-thiones (4a-j) :*

A mixture of (2*E*)-3-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-3-yl]-1-aryl-prop-2-en-1-ones (0.01 mole) and thiourea (0.78 g, 0.01 mole) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on water bath in the presence of alcoholic KOH (1 ml) for 12 h. The solvent was distilled off and the residue was neutralized with dilute HCl and the separated

solid was filtered and crystallized from suitable solvent to give analytical pure products.

4a : 6-[2-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-3-yl]-4-phenylpyrimidine-2(1*H*)-thione : Yield 68%, m.p. 160 °C (Found : C, 61.39; H, 3.21; N, 12.42. $C_{23}H_{14}Cl_2N_4S$ (449.35) required : C, 61.48; H, 3.14; N, 12.47%); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3242 (N-H str.), 3041 (C=C-H str.), 1590 (C=N str.), 1564 (C=S str.), 786 (C-Cl str.); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$), δ , ppm : 6.93 (4H, m, imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-H), 7.36 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.50 (1H, dd, J 8.6, 1.4, Ar-Hf), 7.75 (1H, d, J 8.6, Ar-He), 8.03 (1H, s, pyrimidine-Ha), 8.5 (1H, d, J 1.4, Ar-Hd), 8.92 (1H, s(b), -N-H); EI/MS m/z : 450, 373, 262 (base peak), 221, 192, 164, 138, 78.

4b : 6-[2-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-3-yl]-4-(4-methylphenyl)pyrimidine-2(1*H*)-thione : Yield 54%, m.p. 165 °C (Found : C, 62.14; H, 3.54; N, 12.04. $C_{24}H_{16}Cl_2N_4S$ (463.38) required : C, 62.21; H, 3.48; N, 12.09%); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3308 (N-H str.), 3048 (C=C-H str.), 1618 (C=N, str.), 1584 (C=S str.), 768 (C-Cl str.); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$), δ , ppm : 2.29 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 6.86 (4H, m, imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-H), 7.29 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.45 (1H, dd, J 8.1, 1.3, Ar-Hf), 7.67 (1H, d, J 8.1, Ar-He), 8.06 (1H, s, pyrimidine-Ha), 8.2 (1H, d, J 1.4, Ar-Hd), 8.78 (1H, s(b), -N-H); EI/MS m/z : 464.

4c : 6-[2-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridin-3-yl]-4-(2-methylphenyl)pyrimidine-2(1*H*)-thione : Yield 60%, m.p. 178 °C (Found : C, 62.12; H, 3.55; N, 12.04. $C_{24}H_{16}Cl_2N_4S$ (463.38) required : C, 62.21; H, 3.48; N, 12.09%); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3315 (N-H str.), 3046 (C=C-H str.), 1614 (C=N, str.), 1579 (C=S str.), 772 (C-Cl str.); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$), δ , ppm : 2.32 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 6.89 (4H, m, imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine-H), 7.26 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.48 (1H, dd, J 7.4, 1.6, Ar-Hf), 7.69 (1H, d, J 7.3, Ar-He), 8.02 (1H, s, pyrimidine-Ha), 8.22 (1H, d, J 1.5, Ar-Hd), 8.81 (1H, s(b), -N-H); EI/MS m/z : 464.

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